

UAV Urban Area Vehicle Classification Techniques

G.Padma Ratna(Asst prof.)
Electronics and Communication
Engineering - ANUCET

M.Uma
Electronics and Communication
Engineering - ANUCET

K.Pavan Kumar
Electronics and Communication
Engineering - ANUCET

Sk.Babavali
Electronics and Communication
Engineering - ANUCET

Abstract: The project is based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to classify images captured by UAVs (UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE) in urban areas. We have used the UC MERCED dataset which popular data set for aerial image classification and detection using deep network designer present in MATLAB. We trained the dataset using deep learning architectures based on convolutional neural networks to classify different classes of urban area images (e.g. buildings, vehicles, etc..) using VGG16-net architecture. They pushed the depth to 16–19 weight layers making it approx. — 138 trainable parameters convolutional neural network layers, each of which consists of a pair of two CNN layers of different sizes, Max Pool Layers, Batch Normalization, and Dropout layers with different dropout conditions. The network is further followed by fully connected neural networks to make the learning process easier and faster. We make use of the "SDGM" optimizer and ReLu activation function on Conv2D layers and the Classification Layer on the last (dense) fully connected layer for better representation of data and class prediction.

Keywords—CNN (Convolutional Neural Network), VGG-16Net, Shuffle Net, Squeeze Net, ADAM Optimizer, and MATLAB.

I. INTRODUCTION

UAV stands for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, commonly known as a drone. It is an aircraft without a human pilot onboard, operated either autonomously by computers onboard the aircraft or remotely by a human operator. UAVs come in various shapes, sizes, and configurations, ranging from small consumer drones used for recreational purposes to large military-grade drones used for surveillance, reconnaissance, and combat operations. The use of UAVs has grown significantly in recent years due to advancements in technology, making them more accessible, affordable, and capable. However, their deployment raises various concerns related to safety, privacy, regulatory compliance, and ethical considerations. As such, the development and use of UAVs continue to be subject to stringent regulations and guidelines imposed by aviation authorities worldwide.

Object detection and classification in urban environments is a difficult task using conventional methods. One of the main reasons is the high visual variability of urban objects, which affects the accuracy and generalization of prediction models. Moreover, image acquisition factors such as noise, motion blur, occlusions, lighting variations, reflections, perspective, and geo-location errors can make the task more complex. To overcome these challenges, we can use the data sent by UAVs (unmanned aerial vehicles), which can capture high-resolution aerial images of ground objects. For instance, the data sent by the UAVs can provide more details than the traditional data set, which can enhance the object detection

and classification performance. Processing this data requires advanced computer vision techniques such as deep learning algorithms, which can identify each type of object in a single image accurately. This can help in the precise object detection process in large data sets. One of the common approaches to classifying objects is deep learning, which involves training neural networks to recognize the objects in images. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have achieved promising results in classifying the data acquired by the UAVs, but they still face some difficulties such as classifying different images with similar properties. However, these algorithms need large amounts of data for training. Earlier attempts at solving the classification problem involved defining and extracting certain features from image data sets, which represented most of the data with high confidence. These features aimed to capture interesting information in images such as edges, circles, lines, or a combination of these, which were ideally invariant to translation, scale, and varying light intensities. Examples of such features include BUILDINGS, VEHICLES, ROADS, AGRICULTURAL, AIRPLANE, BASEBALL diamonds, beaches, CHAPARRAL, forests, freeways, GOLF courses, HARBOR, RIVER, runways, OVERPASS, TENNIS COURT, STORAGE TANKS, and PEDESTRIANS.

Once these features were extracted, classifiers such as Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, K-Nearest Neighbors, or Linear Discriminant Analysis were used to determine the membership of an unseen image. However, these methods were time-consuming, and it was hard to define features that captured a wide range of information.

II. RELATED WORK

In the field of remote sensing and agricultural monitoring, several significant contributions have been made utilizing various advanced technologies, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and edge computing. This section reviews pertinent literature that has informed the development and application of these technologies. Yu et al. (2020) utilized Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for urban land cover classification using multispectral and hyperspectral satellite imagery, highlighting the potential of deep learning in remote sensing. Kalman (1960) introduced the Kalman filter, providing a recursive solution to discrete-data linear filtering problems, which has since been adapted for various remote sensing applications. Islam et al. (2020) proposed a vision-based precision agriculture framework employing UAVs for crop monitoring and disease detection, leveraging high-resolution aerial imagery for improved crop manage-

ment. Capolupo et al. (2022) presented a method for detecting Swiss parcel edges and buildings using very high-resolution UAV imagery, demonstrating the potential of UAVs in generating detailed land cover maps. Chen et al. (2022) surveyed deep learning techniques for small object detection in remote sensing images, offering insights into methodologies and challenges critical for environmental monitoring and disaster management. Shi et al. (2023) discussed the challenges and opportunities associated with the integration of edge computing in smart agriculture. Li et al. (2023) provided a comprehensive survey on learning-based scene understanding from remote sensing images. Zhang et al. (2021) utilized CNNs for automated detection and recognition of irrigation pivots from satellite imagery. Finally, Zhao et al. (2021) surveyed drone-based object detection and tracking methods, discussing their advantages and drawbacks. This survey highlights the rapid advancements in UAV technology and its applications in various fields, including surveillance, environmental monitoring, and agriculture.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

- The process involves several key steps, from data acquisition to the application of CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) techniques for object classification.
- We trained a deep learning model on the UC MERCED LAND USE dataset using VGG-16, shuffle and squeeze net. The code was predominantly written in MATLAB and utilized popular deep learning tools in MATLAB such as deep learning designer.
- We used the Adam optimizer and tuned several hyperparameters, including a learning rate of 6001, regularization term of 1×10^{-5} , a batch size of 32, and trained the model for 30 epochs.
- To improve the robustness of our model, we initially employed data augmentation techniques such as random horizontal flips and random affine transformations from the deep learning designer library.
- However, after testing, we found that these techniques did not significantly improve the model's accuracy. Therefore, we decided to limit the code without these techniques.
- Division of the UC merged data into two subsets for model validation: 90% for training and 10% for testing.
- Implementation of various classification algorithms, including VGG-16Net and Shuffle Net and Squeeze Nett o accurately identify objects based on drone images.
- To prevent overfitting during training, we implemented the Early Stopping method. which stops the training process when the validation loss stops improving. However, we also found that this technique did not provide a significant improvement in accuracy for our model.

- However, we also found that this technique did not provide a significant improvement in accuracy for our model, so we decided to remove it from the final version of our code. Overall our deep learning model achieved a test accuracy of 87%, demonstrating its effectiveness in classifying the ten different categories in the UC MERCED LAND USE dataset.

IV. STEPS USED FOR TRAINING

A. Import the dataset

UC MERCED LAND USE included **20 object classes**, spanning people, animals, vehicles, and indoor items. Notable categories were person, bird, car, bottle, and sofa.

Fig:-1 The data set preprocessing.

B. Split the data into training and testing data

The data is split into training and testing data. From the dataset, the whole data is split in such a way that 90% of the data is used for training, and the remaining 10% is used for testing.

C. Training the models

Firstly, MATLAB which contains the deep network designer is used to train the data. In the deep network designer, the popular nets are called VGG-16, SUFFELE NET and SQUEESE NETis used to train the data contained in the data set. When we trained the data for the first time the training accuracy and testing accuracy came as output low which is nearly 60 and 50 respectively. When we trained the same data again the training accuracy and testing accuracy came as output which is nearly 70 and 65 respectively which is more accurate than the first time. Again, when we trained the data set the training accuracy was about to 95 and the testing accuracy was about 87 which is much higher than the first and second results.

V.CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

D. VGG-16 NET

A convolutional neural network is also known as a Convolution Net, which is a kind of artificial neural network. A convolutional neural network has an input layer, an output layer, and various hidden layers. VGG16 is a type of CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) that is one of the best computer vision models to date. The creators of this model evaluated the networks and increased the depth using an architecture with very small (3×3) convolution filters, which showed a significant improvement on the prior-art configurations. They pushed the depth to 16–19 weight layers making it approximately — 138 trainable parameters. VGG16 is an object detection and classification algorithm which can classify 1000 images of 1000 different categories with 92.7% accuracy. It is one of the popular algorithms for image classification and is easy to use with transfer learning. The 16 in VGG16 refers to 16 layers that have weights. In VGG16 there are thirteen convolutional layers, five Max Pooling layers, and three Dense layers which sum up to 21 layers but it has only sixteen weight layers i.e., learnable parameters layer. VGG16 takes input tensor size as 224, 244 with 3 RGB channels. The most unique thing about VGG16 is that instead of having many hyper-parameters they focused on having convolution layers of 3×3 filter with stride 1 and always used the same padding and Max pool layer of 2×2 filter with stride 2.

Fig:-2 VGG-16 Architecture

E. Shuffle Net

Shuffle Net is a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture designed to achieve high accuracy while minimizing computational cost. Shuffle Net was developed to address the increasing demand for deploying CNNs on resource-constrained devices such as mobile phones, IoT devices, and embedded systems. The primary motivation behind Shuffle Net is to reduce computational complexity, memory usage, and model size while maintaining high accuracy in various computer vision tasks. traditional convolutions involve a significant number of parameters and computations, especially as the number of channels increases. Pointwise group

convolution reduces this cost by dividing the input channels into groups and applying convolutions within each group separately.

Fig:-3 Architecture of Shuffle Net

F. Squeeze Net

Squeeze Net is a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture designed to achieve high accuracy while minimizing model size and computational cost. The primary motivation behind Squeeze Net is to reduce model size and computational complexity while maintaining high accuracy in tasks such as image classification. Squeeze Net employs a novel architecture that significantly reduces the number of parameters compared to traditional CNN architectures like Alex Net while maintaining competitive accuracy. It achieves this reduction by replacing traditional 3×3 filters with 1×1 filters (squeeze layers) followed by 3×3 filters (expand layers), reducing the number of parameters without sacrificing expressive power. Squeeze Net also incorporates fire modules, which combine squeeze and expand layers, allowing efficient use of computation and memory.

Fig:-4 Squeeze Net

G. ADAM Optimizer

Adaptive Moment Estimation is an algorithm for optimization technique for gradient descent. The method is really efficient when working with large

problem involving a lot of data or parameters. It requires less memory and is efficient. Intuitively, it is a combination of the ‘gradient descent with momentum’ algorithm and the ‘RMSP’ algorithm.

This algorithm is used to accelerate the gradient descent algorithm by taking into consideration the ‘exponentially weighted average’ of the gradients. Using averages makes the algorithm converge towards the minima in a faster pace. Adam Optimizer inherits the strengths or the positive attributes of the above two methods and builds upon them to give a more optimized gradient descent.

Fig:-5 ADAM Optimizer

VI. RESULTS ANALYSIS

Among the algorithms VGG-16, Shuffle Net and Squeeze Net algorithm with more accuracy is the VGG-16 Net with 96% accuracy.

H. Shuffle Net

The Shuffle Net algorithm got an accuracy of 90%. This algorithm is best used when we want to classify the images in a dataset.

•Traditional Pointwise Convolution:

$$\text{Cost} = H \times W \times C \times KH \times W \times C \times KH \times W \times C \times K$$

•Grouped Convolution:

$$\text{Cost} = H \times W \times C \times KG \times \frac{H \times W \times C \times K}{G} \times GH \times W \times C \times K$$

Fig:-5 Result of Shuffle Net

I. VGG-16 Net

The VGG-16 algorithm got an accuracy of 96%. Among all the algorithms used, VGG-16 got more accuracy with training and testing data.

Fig:-6 Result of VGG-16Net

J. Squeeze Net

The Squeeze net algorithm got an accuracy of 87.2%. for classification of urban area vehicle Classification.

Accuracy is a primary indicator, reflecting the overall rate at which the model correctly predicts the outcome.

Fig:-7 Result Squeeze Net

Metrics	VGG-16	Shuffle Net	Squeeze Net
Training Accuracy	89.42	90.2	91.16
Testing Accuracy	87.19	89.4	87.3
Execution Time (seconds)	0.015	0.14	0.10

K. Confusion Matrix

VII. Conclusion

In recent years, semantic segmentation of aerial data has been a prominent area of research in photogrammetry, remote sensing, and computer vision. Urban applications such as airborne mapping, object positioning, and building extraction from high-resolution aerial images demand accurate and efficient segmentation algorithms. Deep learning models have shown great potential in handling complex scenes and this study focuses on evaluating the semantic segmentation accuracy of UAV-based images in urban areas. The proposed method employs a deep learning framework based on VGG16 Net. This architecture extracts and classifies features through layers of convolution, max pooling, activa-

tion, and concatenation in an end-to-end process.

VIII. References

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